

Predicting the spray drift captured by non-target plants

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Summary

There is interest in developing approaches to higher tier testing, for non-target terrestrial plants, as an alternative to field trials which are expensive and not standardized. Developing modelling or novel experimental methods requires the main factors that determine exposure and biological effect to be taken account of appropriately. Droplet size is likely to be one of the most important parameters to be considered, and so in this study, both modelling and wind tunnel experiments were used to explore some of the factors that influence the size distribution of droplets that reach downwind non-target plants. These factors include wind speed, distance downwind and nozzle design.

Key words: Exposure, droplet size distribution, modelling

Introduction

The effect of pesticide spray drift on non-target plants adjacent to treated fields is currently dealt with in a very simplified way in the European regulatory system. The standard approach for conducting experiments for Tier 1 and Tier 2 assessments is based on plants underneath a track sprayer, usually designed to deliver a volume of around 200 L ha⁻¹ of the dilute product mix. While Tier 1 experiments are done at field rates, the concentration of the product in the applied tank mix is reduced to represent the lower levels of drift exposure that could occur at different distances downwind for Tier 2 experiments.

The concentration used in Tier 2 experiments is based on the Rautmann data (Rautmann, 2001) and is 2.77% of the field rate for an exposure at 1.0 m from the treated area for field crops. For a plant protection product (PPP) applied at 1.0 L ha⁻¹, the effect of drift on a non-target plant at 1.0 m from the edge of the field would therefore be assessed by spraying at 200 L ha⁻¹ with a tank mix of concentration 0.1385 mL ha⁻¹. Thus, to test the ecotoxicological effect of a PPP on non-target plants exposed to spray drift, they are sprayed directly with a low concentration, high volume application, whereas in practice, they would be exposed to a high concentration, low volume spray plume moving sideways.

There has been much discussion over many years about whether the Rautmann data are relevant for all European countries and whether they represent a worst-case scenario for the UK (e.g. Byron & Hamey, 2008) but this is not the focus of this work. However, it is possible to question whether (a) a measure of spray drift based on horizontal ground collectors is appropriate to use for terrestrial plant exposure, and (b) whether an overhead spray is an appropriate way to deliver the exposure in experimental assessments. A higher tier risk

assessment approach for non-target plants would ideally address both factors. Currently, the best higher tier alternative is a field trial, where non-target plants are exposed to spray drift and the biological effect is determined (e.g. Brain *et al.*, 2017; Moore *et al.*, 2021). These are costly, time-consuming and no standard protocol is available, so there is an interest in developing higher tier approaches as alternatives to field trials. Such an approach would need to consider (i) the real quantity of active substance (a.s.) deposited on the plant at different distances downwind and with different levels of drift reduction technology, as well as (ii) a droplet size distribution reaching the plant and (iii) the concentration of a.s. in the spray solution.

The quantity of spray drift to which non-target plants are exposed can be determined through field experiments or estimated using wind tunnel experiments or modelling. A number of spray drift models exist (e.g. Butler Ellis & Miller, 2010) that can predict the quantity of airborne spray reaching a non-target plant. A further modelling step is needed to determine how much of this will be deposited on the plant, and Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) has been proposed as a route to achieving this (Dunne *et al.*, 2023). However, this is not likely to be an easy task, particularly for regulatory use. Accordingly, alternative methods of predicting the proportion of spray that is captured by non-target plants, such as wind tunnel experiments (Isemer *et al.*, 2024), are considered in this study.

Further work would be needed to establish whether the effect of a given dose of a.s. applied in different ways (i.e. a large number of low concentration deposits vs a small number of high concentration deposits) is different, but this is possible as water volume and droplet size can make a difference to the performance of pesticide applications.

In order to reproduce field conditions in either a physical system such as a wind tunnel or spray chamber, or by modelling, we need to understand the factors that influence the collection efficiency, which is defined by Spillman (1984) as the ratio of the volume of droplets caught to the volume of droplets that would have passed through the cross-sectional area of the object during the time of exposure had the obstacle not been there.

Collection efficiency of simple structures was studied by May and Clifford (1967) and later applied to agricultural spray drift (Spillman, 1984). This showed that collection efficiency was a function of the Impact Parameter, P , given by:

$$P = \frac{\rho_d d^2 v}{18\mu W}$$

where ρ_d is the droplet density, d is the droplet diameter, v is the air velocity (assumed the same as droplet velocity when considering spray drift), μ is the dynamic viscosity of air and W is the width (or characteristic dimension) of the object. P was shown to be related to collection efficiency through an empirical relationship, shown in Fig. 1 for some structures. Thus two important variables for defining collection efficiency of a given collector are the diameter of the droplets and the wind speed.

Measurement of droplet size in the field is challenging. Laser diffraction is usually unable to cope with the low airborne concentration of droplets, while droplet imaging will struggle with the smallest droplets and it would take many passes of the sprayer to collect sufficient droplets to define the size distribution.

An alternative approach is therefore through modelling. The SiMoD drift model (Butler Ellis & Miller, 2010) is designed to output only the total quantity of spray at a given location, but it also produces intermediate outputs from which the droplet size distribution at a downwind location can be extracted.

Fig. 1. Collection efficiency of various objects in an air flow, based on data obtained by May and Clifford (1954), taken from Spillman, (1984).

Materials and Methods

Predicting the size distributions of drifting droplets

The model was run for a set of model inputs with nozzles and windspeeds given in Table 1. These scenarios aimed to cover the range of drift conditions that might occur in practice, but also included one scenario representing a field experiment conducted by Bayer Crop Science (unpublished) where deposits on both plants and airborne spray collectors were measured and has previously been used to compare with model predictions. Other model inputs remained constant and were representative of a typical spraying scenario, as used in the field trial.

SiMoD was used to predict droplet size distribution at a height of 0.2 m above the ground (representing what a typical annual non-target plant might be exposed to in a field margin in early spring when many herbicides are sprayed).

Table 1. *Settings for model runs*

Nozzle	TeeJet FF110 03 3.0 bar (medium/fine boundary)			TeeJet FF110 06 2.0 bar (coarse/medium boundary)			TeeJet AIXR 02 at 2.76 bar (Bayer field trial nozzle)			
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Run no.										
Wind speed at 2.0 m height, m s ⁻¹	1.5	2.5	3.5	1.5	2.5	3.5	1.5	2.5	3.5	4.34

Droplet size distributions for model input were obtained using droplet imaging (Visisizer, Oxford Lasers Ltd) and runs 1–6 were based on spraying water alone. For runs 7–10, data for the AIXR 02 nozzle with the tank mix used in the Bayer field trial was obtained. These droplet size data were based on a 10 µm bin size, with the simulated droplet size at the centre of each bin. The lowest bin was 10–20 µm, so the smallest droplet size simulated was 15 µm.

Wind tunnel validation of factors influencing size distribution of drifting spray droplets

Measurement of droplet size distribution of a drifting spray plume under realistic field conditions is challenging, but the Silsoe wind tunnel gives an opportunity to explore some of the basic processes and provide supporting (or otherwise) data for model predictions under controlled conditions where spray density is much higher than in the field.

Laser diffraction (SprayTec Malvern Panalytical Ltd) was used to ensure the smallest droplets were captured. However, laser diffraction needs a threshold airborne concentration to trigger, and with a moving nozzle, this threshold is difficult to achieve. Fig. 2 shows the wind tunnel setup, with the two-nozzle boom travelling across the image from left to right and right to left (multiple passes to ensure a sufficiently long sampling time); wind direction is out of the page.

Fig. 2. Malvern SprayTec (foreground) in the wind tunnel at a distance of 1.25 m from the downwind nozzle and 0.57 m below the spray tip. The red line indicates the sampling volume (added into the picture later).

Measurements at the distances, wind speeds, boom height and sample height that matched the model runs were not possible as there was insufficient spray concentration. Some trial-and-error runs were conducted, and eventually the settings in Table 2 were identified where the effect of distance, nozzle and wind speed within a similar range could be evaluated.

Table 2. *Settings for wind tunnel experiment to determine main factors that influence spray drift droplet size at a given distance from the field*

Wind speeds at boom height, m s ⁻¹	1.13*	2.65*
Nozzles	FF110 03 at 3 bar	AIXR 02 at 2.76 bar
Distances from nozzle, m	1.25	3.20
Measurement height, m	0.06	0.06
Boom height, m	0.57	0.57
Speed, km h ⁻¹	9	9
No of nozzles	Two-nozzle boom	Two-nozzle boom

*Equivalent to 1.5 and 3.0 m s⁻¹ at 2 m height in the field

Results

Model simulations

A comparison of the volumetric droplet size distributions from the three nozzles used for the simulations is shown in Fig. 2. Table 3 shows the D_{10} , Volume median diameter (VMD) and D_{90} predicted by the model, i.e. the droplet size for which 10%, 50% and 90% respectively, of liquid volume, is in smaller droplets.

Calculated VMDs at 0.2 m above the ground are also given in Fig. 4. VMDs vary from 26 to 71 μm . Data clusters together, with the biggest differences due to wind speed and distance, and only small differences due to nozzle.

Fig. 3. Initial droplet size distributions for the three nozzle/pressure settings representing different spray qualities and an air-included nozzle as given in Table 1.

Table 3. *Characteristic droplet sizes of drifting spray plume at 0.2 m above the ground for three nozzles and a range of wind speeds and distances between 1 and 15 m downwind (model predictions)*

Nozzle		FF11003 at 3.0 bar			FF11006 at 2.0 bar			AIXR 02 at 2.76 bar			
Distance downwind, m	Wind speed, m.s ⁻¹										
		1.5	2.5	3.5	1.5	2.5	3.5	1.5	2.5	3.5	4.34
D₁₀, μm	1	20.0	27.0	32.1	19.1	28.5	34.7	25.0	30.0	36.5	40.5
	5	15.6	21.5	25.8	15.6	22.2	27.2	25.0	25.0	29.2	32.7
	10	15.0	19.1	24.4	15.1	19.5	26.2	25.0	25.0	28.0	29.1
	15	15.0	18.6	23.5	15.0	19.6	23.9	25.0	25.0	26.8	28.7
VMD μm	1	42.5	51.2	60.1	38.0	54.0	64.0	38.1	53.6	63.5	70.9
	5	29.3	41.3	48.5	29.7	41.5	49.6	30.7	42.4	51.0	57.6
	10	27.7	38.4	45.3	27.9	38.5	46.9	29.5	39.5	47.6	52.8
	15	26.4	37.4	43.3	26.2	36.5	45.0	28.2	38.2	45.5	50.7
D₉₀, μm	1	310.8	79.6	93.1	59.2	84.2	100.1	57.3	80.4	94.4	104.5
	5	44.4	61.4	72.3	45.0	63.0	74.4	45.0	62.7	74.5	84.6
	10	42.0	55.5	64.9	42.5	56.0	68.8	42.8	58.6	70.7	76.5
	15	40.9	54.4	63.8	42.0	54.5	66.8	41.3	54.8	66.8	75.0

Fig. 4. The effect of distance downwind, wind speed and initial droplet size on predicted VMD

Wind tunnel measurements

Table 4 shows the spray statistics for the eight runs conducted in the wind tunnel. Fig. 5 shows the relationship between VMD of the drifting spray plume and nozzle, wind speed and distance downwind.

Table 4. *Spray statistics from wind tunnel measurements*

	Distance, m	wind speed, m s ⁻¹	D ₁₀ , μm	VMD μm	D ₉₀ , μm
FF110 03 at 3.0 bar	1.25	1.13	48.97	87.26	136.76
	3.2	1.13	39.00	67.17	105.69
	1.25	2.65	76.27	121.26	188.15
	3.2	2.65	45.30	77.78	114.26
AIXR110 02 at 2.76 bar	1.25	1.13	71.70	95.36	121.07
	3.2	1.13	44.78	60.30	73.34
	1.25	2.65	103.36	133.03	167.42
	3.2	2.65	55.00	79.83	114.67

Fig. 5. VMD of downwind spray drift from the measurements made in the wind tunnel using the settings given in Table 4.

Discussion

The experimental data supports the model predictions in principle, although higher VMDs were measured (Table 3) than were predicted (Table 2). This was to be expected as the settings were different, with the measurement height closer to the floor of the wind tunnel (0.06 m vs 0.2 m) which might be expected to include more large droplets. Also, model predictions were for a full boom, where the distances from the furthest nozzles are greater, resulting in more smaller droplets. It is, however, clear that the effect of nozzle is much less than the effect of distance and wind speed on droplet size characteristics. It would be possible to do some further model runs to match the experimental measurements, although it is known that there are always difficulties in predicting droplet characteristics very close to the nozzle because the nozzle characteristics (such as fan angle, droplet velocities and entrained air) can dominate.

In order to develop a testing approach as a refinement option for higher tier risk assessments for non-target terrestrial plants as an alternative to drift field trials, we need to understand and reproduce the main factors that influence the exposure and the subsequent biological effect. The size of droplets is likely to be one of the most important factors because this will strongly influence the quantity of spray that is retained on the plant. In addition, the biological effect is, for some plant protection products at least, influenced by the droplet size of the application (i.e. fine sprays are often thought to be more effective than coarse sprays).

This study has shown that, perhaps contrary to initial expectations, the droplet size distribution of the drifting spray mainly depends on the wind speed and the distance downwind but much less on the original size distribution. The boom height is expected to also have an influence, but was not explored in this study. On the other hand, it is known that the original droplet size distribution clearly affects the quantity of spray drift.

To develop this approach further, an experimental set-up to deliver a droplet size distribution representative of drift at different distances downwind from the field would have to be designed. The droplet size distribution would need to be related to the distance downwind, but could be designed to be appropriate to a fixed boom height and wind speed. If the experimental set-up needs to take account of drift-reducing nozzles, then this requires adjustment of only the quantity of spray delivered to the non-target plant and not the spray quality.

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